

Title:

Using Private Network (WireGuard) For Sending Data (Publishing) To The MQTT Broker

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Keywords:

IoT Network Security, MQTT Publishing, EMQX, WireGuard, VPN, Edge Computing, ESP32

Abstract:

The use of VPN-based private networking to improve MQTT broker security in Internet of Things infrastructures is examined in this study. It illustrates how private network tunnelling successfully reduces the risks of port discovery, unauthorised access, and distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks in both Edge and Cloud environments by using WireGuard to isolate broker communications.

1. Introduction:

This article presents an independent exploration of **VPN-based private networking** using **WireGuard** to enhance the security of MQTT brokers in IoT infrastructures. The work contributes to the broader research area of Edge and Cloud Computing Security by demonstrating a practical approach to securing broker communications through **network isolation and encrypted tunnelling**.

Regarding my Research field of Edge & Cloud Computing Security, I already wrote a small post on the idea of using a private network (VPN) for connecting IoT devices to clouds, brokers, etc. I came to know its use when I was learning cybersecurity via Hack The Box, as cybersecurity is my main point of view around which this cloud and IoT security revolves.

2. Background:

2.1. MQTT And Its Broker Exposure Risks:

MQTT is widely used for telemetry due to its lightweight nature and low bandwidth usage. Its efficient for IoT world than HTTPS as performance benchmarks show that MQTT is on average **25 times faster** than HTTP even when using persistent connections (Flespi, 2018).

2.1.1. EMQX (MQTT Broker):

So, let's Consider a Simple Setup for an IoT Device (like gas sensors, temp sensors, etc). These devices communicate over the MQTT (IoT) protocol and transfer the data to a broker. In my case, it was **EMQX (<https://www.emqx.com/en>)**. It is widely used with **1,000+ global customers, with 400K+ cluster deployments globally, with 20M+ connected vehicles, and with 250M+ connected IoT devices**, and is very good for experiments and personal projects. If someone has the intention of large-scale production deployment, they can get a free enterprise trial license for a limited time, and then can get it by paying. I would recommend using that because it uses quite good features as :

High-performance MQTT with advanced security, governance, and data integration for regulated or air-gapped environments.

- All features of the EMQX open source core
- Multiple IoT protocols support
- Data integration with **40+ enterprise systems**
- Data persistence and bridging
- Management & monitoring centre

2.1.2. Broker Exposure Risks

However, MQTT brokers, such as **EMQX**, if deployed over publicly accessible interface can be vulnerable to:

- Unauthorized access and privilege escalation
- Credential stuffing and brute-force attacks
- Port discovery and service enumeration
- Denial of Service (DoS/DDoS) attacks

2.2. WireGuard Overview

According to [Wikipedia](#):

“WireGuard is a communication protocol and free and open-source software that implements encrypted virtual private networks. It aims to be simpler and better performing than IPsec and OpenVPN.”

3. Case Study: AgroSense Smart Greenhouses

Let us take a case study of a fictional yet representative organization, **AgroSense** and which runs and operates multiple smart greenhouses across different regions. Each greenhouse is equipped with IoT sensors that will monitor critical environmental parameters needed for crop health - such as temperature, humidity, soil moisture, CO2 level, and light intensity.

The goals are:

- Collect data in real time from these sensors.
- Transmit it to the cloud securely via an MQTT broker.
- Visualize and analyse it on a dashboard.
- Trigger **automated actions**, i.e., like turning on fans or starting irrigation pumps when certain thresholds are reached.

4. System Architecture

4.1. Layers

The layers involved here now will be:

- **IoT Layer (Edge Devices):** ESP32 / Raspberry Pi devices
- **MQTT Layer:** EMQX Broker on a Cloud VM
- **Cloud Layer:** Application and data processing services
- **Application Layer:** Web dashboard and analytics platform

4.2. Broker Exposure

Now consider this action of recording the temperature of the greenhouse. After reading the temperature and humidity values, the **IoT Side (Edge Devices)** need to send the Data via **MQTT to the broker (EMQX)**. The broker is running on a virtual machine. For MQTT operation and management, AgroSense’s broker typically uses:

- Port 22 — SSH
- Port 18083 — EMQX Dashboard
- Port 1883 — MQTT (non-TLS)
- Port 8883 — MQTT (TLS-secured)

The ports along with services are used by the AgroSense Team.

These ports if open to the internet, create potential attack surfaces. Attackers can discover them through simple type of network scanning which can further lead to brute-force, DDoS attacks, or exploitation attempts by hackers.

The Public IP address/interface being used by the broker & cloud (AgroSense) team can be a main source of attention for hackers and attackers. But what if AgroSense team's data is being transmitted via a **secure and private network using WireGuard or OpenVPN**, then the chances of VM discovery and open ports discovery will be reduced greatly.

5. Proposed Solution: VPN-Based Isolation Using WireGuard

My proposed solution is based on the use of this method of encapsulation of the broker communications and networking within a WireGuard-based private network, all MQTT, SSH, and management connections are transmitted securely through a VPN tunnel. This will turn the EMQX broker nearly invisible to unauthorized external entities.

5.1. Configuration Example:

The **Broker VM will be running WireGuard** (<https://www.wireguard.com/>), and so will be the **AgroSense Computers** by specifying the endpoints and using private and public keys.

Broker VM Configuration

```
[Interface]
Address = 10.10.0.1/24
PrivateKey = (Broker_VM_PRIVATE_KEY)
ListenPort = 51820
```

```
[Peer]
PublicKey = (TEAM_PUBLIC_KEY)
AllowedIPs = 10.10.0.2/32
```

Team (Client) Configuration

[Interface]

Address = 10.10.0.1/24

PrivateKey = (TEAM_PRIVATE_KEY)

[Peer]

PublicKey = (TEAM_PUBLIC_KEY)

Endpoint = BROKER_VM_PUBLIC_IP:51820

AllowedIPs = 10.10.0.0/24, 192.168.0.0/16

PersistentKeepalive = 25

The **VM Instance (IaaS) Settings** are configured to work with security rules in networking to allow only one **UDP Port 51820** to accept incoming connections (Ingress) rule. This will make the SSH and other Broker MQTT services only accessible via the WireGuard Network i.e. by AgroSense.

We will also apply a **Linux firewall internally** to allow other connections through WireGuard explicitly and deny direct connections.

```
sudo ufw allow in on wg0 to any port 22
sudo ufw allow in on wg0 to any port 1883
sudo ufw allow in on wg0 to any port 18083
sudo ufw deny 22/tcp
sudo ufw deny 1883/tcp
sudo ufw deny 18083/tcp
sudo ufw enable
```

Now internal communication is allowed through the VPN interface (wg0).

6. iptables Configuration

To ensure proper packet forwarding and NAT handling for WireGuard Traffic:

```
sudo iptables -I INPUT -p udp --dport 51820 -j ACCEPT
sudo iptables -I FORWARD -i wg0 -j ACCEPT
sudo iptables -I FORWARD -o wg0 -j ACCEPT
sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o ens3 -j MASQUERADE
```

7. Security Impact and Risk Mitigation

Major Threats Addressed:

Threat	Mitigation via WireGuard
Unauthorized broker access	Broker hidden behind VPN
Dashboard brute-force	UI accessible only through VPN
DDoS on open ports	Public ports closed; VPN UDP only
Data interception	Encrypted private tunnel
Credential theft	No exposed endpoints to harvest
Lateral movement	Private subnet isolation

Attacker's Perspective (Before vs After):

Before:

```
nmap -p 22,1883,18083 x.x.x.x
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
1883/tcp  open  mqtt
18083/tcp open  emqx-dashboard
```

After VPN Isolation:

```
nmap -p 22,1883,18083 x.x.x.x
PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    filtered ssh
1883/tcp  filtered mqtt
18083/tcp filtered unknown
```

UDP port 51820 (WireGuard) also gives response “open|filtered”, making it inconspicuous to someone scanning the interface.

8. Discussion

The application of VPN based network isolation introduces minimal performance overhead while giving substantial security benefits. WireGuard simplicity and efficiency make it well-suited and nicely supported for edge devices and containerized broker, compared to heavier **VPN solutions such as OpenVPN or IPsec**.

Additionally, using internal IP addressing (e.g 10.10.0.0/24) decouples public IP exposure, allowing scalable multiple broker topologies within private overlays.

9. Conclusion

This study explains a **VPN-based approach** to securing and protecting MQTT brokers within IoT infrastructures. By isolating broker communications inside a WireGuard private network, exposure to common attacks such as **port scanning (nmap), credential theft, and DoS** is drastically reduced.

This concept we discussed above, while being simple to deploy and implement, aligns closely with modern **Zero Trust** and Defence-in-Depth principles and can be extended further and implemented on large scale through integration with **kubernetes, edge gateways, or SD-WAN-based** network segmentation.

10. References

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